

and Spain that could be considered "regions" in each of those Member States.

On April 20, 2004, we published in the **Federal Register** (69 FR 21042–21047, Docket No. 98–090–7) a final rule that recognized France and Spain as regions in which CSF does not exist and affirmed the designation of the Commune in France and the Comarca in Spain as the smallest administrative jurisdictions within those Member States that we will use for regionalization purposes.

We are giving notice that a draft document entitled "APHIS Considerations on the Identification of Administrative Units for Certain Member States of the European Union" is available for public review and are requesting comments on the draft document for 60 days. In the draft document we identify the smallest administrative jurisdictions in 11 Member States that we would use to regionalize those Member States in the event of future animal disease outbreaks. As discussed in the draft document, we believe that each of those jurisdictions is the smallest that can be demonstrated to have effective oversight of normal animal movements into, out of, and within that Member State, and that, in association with national authorities, if necessary, has effective control over animal movements and animal diseases locally. For the sake of convenience, the draft document and any future rulemakings will refer to these jurisdictions as "administrative units" (AUs).

The draft document designates AUs for 11 Member States within the EU region. These Member States are: Austria, Belgium, Denmark, Finland, Greece, Ireland, Luxembourg, the Netherlands, Portugal, Sweden, and the United Kingdom. Because APHIS considers the entire territory of Luxembourg to be the smallest possible administrative jurisdiction with effective control over animal movement and control of animal disease locally, the entire country of Luxembourg will be considered one AU. The draft document also reidentifies the AU for Italy as the Aziende Sanitarie Locali (Local Health Unit). In the event of an animal disease outbreak, APHIS could regionalize a Member State to the AU level specified in our draft document. Although addressed in the document in the context of the specific disease, CSF, the concept of regionalization to the AU level is not disease specific.

Accessing the Draft Document on the Internet

The draft document may be viewed on the may be viewed on the EDOCKET Web site (see **ADDRESSES** above for instructions for accessing EDOCKET). You may request paper copies of the draft document by calling or writing to the person listed under **FOR FOR FURTHER INFORMATION CONTACT**. Please refer to the title of the draft document when requesting copies. The draft document is also available for review in our reading room (information on the location and hours of the reading room is listed under the heading **ADDRESSES** at the beginning of this notice).

Done in Washington, DC, this 18th day of April 2005.

W. Ron DeHaven,

Administrator, Animal and Plant Health Inspection Service.

[FR Doc. E5–1881 Filed 4–20–05; 8:45 am]

BILLING CODE 3410–34–P

ANTITRUST MODERNIZATION COMMISSION

Public Meeting

AGENCY: Antitrust Modernization Commission.

ACTION: Notice of public meeting.

SUMMARY: The Antitrust Modernization Commission will hold a public meeting on May 9, 2005. The purpose of the meeting is for the Antitrust Modernization Commission to approve plans (including proposed requests for public comment and public hearings) for studying issues selected by the Commission in its January 13 and March 24, 2005, meetings.

DATES: May 9, 2005, 1 p.m. to 3:30 p.m. Interested members of the public may attend. Registration is not required.

ADDRESSES: Federal Trade Commission, Conference Center Rooms A & B, 601 New Jersey Avenue, NW., Washington, DC.

FOR FURTHER INFORMATION CONTACT: Andrew J. Heimert, Executive Director & General Counsel, Antitrust Modernization Commission; telephone: (202) 233–0701; e-mail: info@amc.gov. Mr. Heimert is also the Designated Federal Officer (DFO) for the Antitrust Modernization Commission.

SUPPLEMENTARY INFORMATION: The purpose of this meeting is for the Antitrust Modernization Commission to approve plans prepared by its study groups for studying issues selected by the Commission in its January 13 and March 24, 2005, meetings, including

proposed requests for public comment and public hearings. Materials relating to the meeting will be made available on the Commission's Web site (<http://www.amc.gov>) in advance of the meeting.

The AMC has called this meeting pursuant to its authorizing statute and the Federal Advisory Committee Act. Antitrust Modernization Commission Act of 2002, Public Law No. 107–273, section 11058(f), 116 Stat. 1758, 1857; Federal Advisory Committee Act, 5 U.S.C. App., section 10(a)(2); 41 CFR § 102–3.150 (2004).

Dated: April 18, 2005.

By direction of Deborah A. Garza, Chair of the Antitrust Modernization Commission.

Approved by Designated Federal Officer.

Andrew J. Heimert,

Executive Director & General Counsel, Antitrust Modernization Commission.

[FR Doc. 05–8026 Filed 4–20–05; 8:45 am]

BILLING CODE 6820–YM–P

DEPARTMENT OF THE INTERIOR

Fish and Wildlife Service

DEPARTMENT OF COMMERCE

National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration

[I.D. 020705D]

Endangered and Threatened Wildlife and Plants; Initiation of a 5–Year Review of Listed Sea Turtles

AGENCIES: Fish and Wildlife Service (FWS), Interior, and National Marine Fisheries Service (NMFS), National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration (NOAA), Commerce.

ACTION: Notice of 5–year status review of sea turtles.

SUMMARY: We, the FWS and NMFS (collectively the Services), announce a 5–year review of the green turtle (*Chelonia mydas*), hawksbill turtle (*Eretmochelys imbricata*), Kemp's ridley turtle (*Lepidochelys kempii*), leatherback turtle (*Dermochelys coriacea*), loggerhead turtle (*Caretta caretta*), and olive ridley turtle (*Lepidochelys olivacea*) under the Endangered Species Act of 1973, as amended (ESA). A 5–year review is a periodic process conducted to ensure that the listing classification of a species is accurate. It is based on the best scientific and commercial data available at the time of the review. New data are available since the last reviews were completed in 1985 for the green turtle and in 1995 for the hawksbill, Kemp's

ridley, leatherback, loggerhead, and olive ridley turtles. Therefore, the Services are initiating a 5-year status review and soliciting information and comments pertaining to these species from any interested party. Based on the results of this 5-year review, we will make the requisite findings under the ESA.

DATES: Written comments and information related to this 5-year review must be received by July 20, 2005.

ADDRESSES: Written comments and information should be addressed to Barbara Schroeder, National Sea Turtle Coordinator, Marine Mammal and Marine Turtle Conservation Division, NMFS Office of Protected Resources, 1315 East-West Highway, Silver Spring, MD, 20910; or by fax (301) 427-2522, or by e-mail at:

Seaturtle.Statusreview@noaa.gov. Information received in response to this notice will be available for public inspection, by appointment, during normal business hours, at the above address.

FOR FURTHER INFORMATION CONTACT: At NMFS, Barbara Schroeder (ph. 301-713-1401, fax 301-713-0376, e-mail *barbara.schroeder@noaa.gov*) or at FWS, Sandy MacPherson (ph. 904-232-2580, fax 904-232-2404, e-mail *Sandy_MacPherson@fws.gov*).

SUPPLEMENTARY INFORMATION:

Background

Six species of sea turtles are listed under the ESA. In 1970, the hawksbill was listed as endangered (35 FR 8495); the Kemp's ridley as endangered (35 FR 18320); and the leatherback as endangered (35 FR 8495). In 1978 (43 FR 32808), the green turtle was listed as endangered for breeding colonies in Florida and on the Pacific coast of Mexico and threatened elsewhere; the loggerhead as threatened; and the olive ridley as endangered for the breeding colony population on the Pacific coast of Mexico and threatened elsewhere.

Under the ESA, section 4(c)(2)(A) requires that we conduct a review of listed species at least once every 5 years. Then, on the basis of such reviews, we determine under section 4(c)(2)(B) whether or not any species should be removed from the threatened or endangered species list (List), or reclassified from endangered to threatened or from threatened to endangered. Removing a species from the List must be supported by the best scientific and commercial data available and under 50 CFR 424.11(d), only considered if data substantiate that the

species is neither endangered nor threatened for one or more of the following reasons: (1) The species is considered extinct; (2) the species is considered to be recovered; and/or (3) the original data available when the species was listed, or the interpretation of such data, were in error. Any change in Federal classification would require a separate rulemaking process. The regulations in 50 CFR 424.21 require that we publish a notice in the **Federal Register** announcing species currently under active review.

The 5-year review provides an opportunity to review whether the listed entity is appropriately identified and delineated, determine appropriate classification, and recommend changes, as appropriate. In accordance with the February 7, 1996, Policy Regarding the Recognition of Distinct Vertebrate Population Segments (DPS) (61 FR 4722), the DPS policy will be considered and applied as appropriate during the 5-year review. The DPS policy states that "Any Distinct Population Segment of a vertebrate taxon that was listed prior to implementation of the DPS policy will be reevaluated on a case-by-case basis as recommendations are made to change the listing status for that distinct population segment." For a population to be listed under the ESA as a DPS, three elements are considered: (1) The discreteness of the population segment in relation to the remainder of the species to which it belongs; (2) the significance of the population segment to the species to which it belongs; and (3) the population segment's conservation status in relation to the ESA's standards for listing (i.e., is the population segment endangered or threatened?). Distinct population segments of vertebrate species, as well as subspecies of all listed species, may be proposed for separate reclassification or for removal from the List. The DPS policy will be applied during the 5-year review.

Previous 5-year reviews were conducted in 1985 and in 1995. However, in the 1995 review, the green turtle review was not completed. This notice announces our active review of the green, hawksbill, Kemp's ridley, leatherback, loggerhead, and olive ridley turtles.

Public Solicitation of New Information

To ensure that the 5-year review is complete and based on the best available scientific and commercial information, we are soliciting new information from the public, concerned governmental agencies, Tribes, the scientific community, industry,

environmental entities, and any other interested parties concerning the status of green turtles, hawksbill turtles, Kemp's ridley turtles, leatherback turtles, loggerhead turtles, and olive ridley turtles.

The 5-year review considers the best scientific and commercial data and all new information that has become available since the listing determination or most recent status review. Categories of requested information include: (1) Species biology, including but not limited to, population trends, distribution, abundance, demographics, and genetics; (2) habitat conditions, including but not limited to, amount, distribution, and suitability; (3) conservation measures that have been implemented that benefit the species; (4) threat status and trends; and (5) other new information, data, or corrections, including but not limited to, taxonomic or nomenclatural changes, identification of erroneous information contained in the List, and improved analytical methods.

See **ADDRESSES** for where to submit comments and materials for this 5-year review. Our practice is to make comments, including names and home addresses of respondents, available for public review during regular business hours. Individual respondents may request that we withhold a respondent's identity. If you wish us to withhold your name or address, you must write this request prominently at the beginning of your comment. We will withhold this information to the extent consistent with applicable law. We will make all submissions from organizations or businesses, and from individuals identifying themselves as representatives or officials of organizations or businesses, available for public inspection in their entirety. Comments and materials received will be available for public inspection, by appointment, during normal business hours (see **ADDRESSES** section). The Services will continue to accept new information on listed sea turtles outside of the comment period for this 5-year review.

Authority

This document is published under the authority of the ESA of 1973, as amended (16 U.S.C. 1531 *et seq.*).

March 25, 2005.

Sam D. Hamilton,

Regional Director, Southeast Region, Fish and Wildlife Service.

Dated: March 3, 2005.

P. Michael Payne,

Chief, Marine Mammal and Marine Turtle Conservation Division, National Marine Fisheries Service.

March 9, 2005.

Ren Lohofener,

Acting Regional Director, Southwest Region, Fish and Wildlife Service.

[FR Doc. 05-8032 Filed 4-20-05; 8:45 am]

BILLING CODE 3510-22-S

DEPARTMENT OF COMMERCE

National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration

[I.D. 041805A]

Fisheries of the Exclusive Economic Zone Off Alaska; Notice of Crab Rationalization Program Public Workshop

AGENCY: National Marine Fisheries Service (NMFS), National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration (NOAA), Commerce.

ACTION: Notice of public workshop.

SUMMARY: NMFS will present a public workshop on the new Crab Rationalization Program (Program) for participants in the Bering Sea and Aleutian Islands (BSAI) king and Tanner crab fisheries. At this workshop, NMFS will provide an overview of the Program, discuss the key Program elements, provide information on the application process, and answer questions. This workshop is specifically intended to address issues related to the Arbitration System portion of the Program. NMFS is conducting this public workshop to provide assistance to fishery participants in complying with the requirements of this new Program.

DATES: Workshop will be held May 9, 2005. See **SUPPLEMENTARY INFORMATION**.

ADDRESSES: Workshop will be held in Seattle, WA.

FOR FURTHER INFORMATION CONTACT: Sheela McLean, 907-586-7032 or sheela.mclean@noaa.gov.

SUPPLEMENTARY INFORMATION: On March 2, 2005, NMFS published a final rule implementing the Crab Rationalization Program (Program) as Amendments 18 and 19 to the Fishery Management Plan for Bering Sea/ Aleutian Islands King and Tanner Crabs. In January 2004, the

U.S. Congress amended section 313(j) of the Magnuson-Stevens Act through the Consolidated Appropriations Act of 2004 (Pub. L. No. 108-199, section 801). As amended, section 313(j)(1) requires the Secretary to approve and implement by regulation the Program, as it was approved by the North Pacific Fishery Management Council (Council) between June 2002 and April 2003, and all trailing amendments, including those reported to Congress on May 6, 2003. In June 2004, the Council consolidated its actions on the Program into the Council motion, which is contained in its entirety in Amendment 18. Additionally, in June 2004, the Council developed Amendment 19, which represents minor changes necessary to implement the Program. The Notice of Availability for these amendments was published in the **Federal Register** on September 1, 2004 (69 FR 53397). NMFS approved Amendments 18 and 19 on November 19, 2004. NMFS published a proposed rule to implement Amendments 18 and 19 in the **Federal Register** on October 29, 2004 (69 FR 63200).

NMFS conducted four public workshops in March and April in Alaska, Oregon, and Washington to provide assistance to fishery participants in complying with the requirements of this new Program (70 FR 10992). At these workshops, NMFS provided an overview of the Program, discussed the key Program elements, and provide information on the application process.

The May 9, 2005 workshop is intended to specifically focus on the Arbitration System. Elements related to economic data collection, monitoring and enforcement, electronic reporting, quota share and individual fishing quota application and transfer provisions, the appeals process, fee collection, and the loan program may be addressed secondarily. Additionally, NMFS will answer questions from workshop participants. For further information on the Crab Rationalization Program, please visit the NMFS Alaska Region Internet site at www.fakr.noaa.gov.

Workshop Dates, Times, and Locations

NMFS will hold the public workshop as follows:

Monday, May 9, 2005, 10 a.m.–4 p.m. Pacific Standard Time (PST)—Leif Erickson Hall, 2245 Northwest 57th Street, Seattle, WA.

Special Accommodations

This workshop is physically accessible to people with disabilities. Requests for special accommodations should be directed to Sheela McLean

(see **FOR FURTHER INFORMATION CONTACT**) at least five working days before the workshop date.

Dated: April 18, 2005.

Emily Menashes,

Acting Director, Office of Sustainable Fisheries, National Marine Fisheries Service.

[FR Doc. E5-1874 Filed 4-20-05; 8:45 am]

BILLING CODE 3510-22-S

DEPARTMENT OF COMMERCE

National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration

[I.D. 041505G]

Gulf of Mexico Fishery Management Council; Public Meetings

AGENCY: National Marine Fisheries Service (NMFS), National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration (NOAA), Commerce.

ACTION: Notice of public meetings.

SUMMARY: The Gulf of Mexico Fishery Management Council will convene public meetings. See **SUPPLEMENTARY INFORMATION** for specific meeting schedule.

DATES: The meetings will be held May 9 - 12, 2005.

ADDRESSES: These meetings will be held at the Palace Casino Resort, 158 Howard Avenue, Biloxi, MS.

Council address: Gulf of Mexico Fishery Management Council, 3018 North U.S. Highway 301, Suite 1000, Tampa, FL 33619.

FOR FURTHER INFORMATION CONTACT: Wayne E. Swingle, Executive Director, Gulf of Mexico Fishery Management Council; telephone: 813.228.2815.

SUPPLEMENTARY INFORMATION:

Council Meetings - Schedule

Wednesday, May 11, 2005

8:30 a.m. – Convene.

8:45 a.m. – 12 Noon - Receive public testimony on (a) Final Shrimp Amendment 13/EA and (b) Exempted fishing permits (if any).

1 p.m. – 1:30 p.m. - Receive a report on the Administration's Ocean Action Plan.

1:30 p.m. – 2:45 p.m. - Receive a presentation on major law enforcement issues regarding red snapper violations and illegal seafood imports.

2:45 p.m. – 3 p.m. - Receive the National State Fishery Directors' Meeting report.

3 p.m. – 4 p.m. - Receive the Shrimp Management Committee report.

4 p.m. – 4:15 p.m. - Receive the AP Selection Committee Report (CLOSED SESSION).